

ABSTRACT BOOK

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COMORBIDITY OF CHRONIC PAIN AND MENTAL
HEALTH DISORDERS: BREAKING THE CYCLE

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Pain Detect scores suggested a possible neuropathic component. The Brief Pain Inventory highlighted significant negative impacts on mood and enjoyment of life.

Conclusions: Pain syndrome is a frequent complication in MS, affecting 62.2% of patients in our study. The nature of pain in MS suggests a potential neuropathic component, necessitating comprehensive pain management strategies to improve patient quality of life.

I-A.22

AN ANALYSIS OF CLINICAL DIAGNOSTIC TOOL FOR THE ASSESSMENT OF CHRONIC NEUROPATHIC PAIN IN PRIMARY CARE

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Background and aims: The International Association for the Study of Pain (IASP) defines neuropathic pain as, 'pain that arises as a direct consequence of a lesion or diseases affecting the somatosensory system.' This can manifest in different forms such as burning/shooting pains, parasthesias, hypoesthesia, hyperalgesia, and allodynia. According to the National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE), the prevalence of chronic neuropathic pain in the UK is 8.2%. Accurate diagnosis is vital for addressing this debilitating condition. Primary care serves as a chief entity for early detection and acts as a gateway for optimal long-term management. This research project aims to identify the most effective methods for diagnosing neuropathic pain.

Methods: A literature review was conducted using Web of Science platform with key terms such as 'clinical diagnostics', 'chronic neuropathic pain,' 'primary care,' and 'assessment tools.' Articles for analysis were selected from high-impact journals including American Journal of Medicine, the Journal of IASP, and Lancet Neurology.

Results: This review recognised that integrating screening tools with comprehensive patient history-taking and physical examination markedly improved the accuracy of neuropathic pain diagnoses. The research revealed that the Douleur Neuropathique 4 (DN4) and the Leeds Assessment of Neuropathic Symptoms and Signs Scale (LANSS scale) are the most effective screening instruments for diagnosing neuropathic pain.

Conclusions: The synergistic approach allows for a more nuanced understanding of the patient's symptoms. Ascertaining a true diagnosis is crucial for successful management and better patient prognoses. Screening tools play a pivotal role in consolidating diagnoses within primary care.

I-A.23

PAIN IN CHRONIC STROKE - A SINGLE CENTER CROSS-SECTIONAL STUDY

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Background and aims: Pain is a common occurrence in chronic stroke phase and may attribute to the worsening of functional status and quality of life. The aim of this study was to evaluate different pain subtypes in chronic stroke patients and the effect of chronic pain on the rehabilitation outcome, functional and emotional status and the quality of life.

Methods: This research was designed as a prospective single center cross-sectional study. Forty five in-hospital stroke patients were included in the study. Pain intensity was measured by Numeric Rating Scale (NRS), while pain characteristics were assessed by Douleur Neuropathique en 4 Questions (DN4) scale. Functional status was evaluated by Barthel index and Fugl-Meyer assessment and quality of life by SF-36 tool. Emotional functioning was estimated by The Depression, Anxiety and Stress Scale (DASS 21).

Results: The results showed a high prevalence of pain among patients in the chronic phase of stroke (46.7%), with various types of pain present. Neuropathic pain according to DN4 scale was present in 36% of patients. The presence of pain was associated with worse functional recovery, reduced independence in activities of daily living, and the presence of depression, anxiety, and stress. A strong correlation was found between pain levels and life quality (p=0.557).

Conclusions: Pain in the chronic phase of stroke is a significant issue due to its frequency and its impact on rehabilitation outcomes, functional recovery, and overall quality of life. Timely diagnosis and treatment of post-stroke pain are crucial for successful rehabilitation and functional recovery of patients.

I-A.26

IS AUTONOMIC FUNCTION ASSOCIATED WITH (CENTRAL) PAIN PROCESSING IN INDIVIDUALS WITH CHRONIC PAIN? A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW

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Background and aims: Dysfunctions of the autonomic nervous system (ANS) are hypothesized to be associated with altered central pain processing (CPP). Altered CPP characterizes nociplastic pain, which is common in non-specific chronic pain conditions. However, the exact interaction between ANS function and chronic pain remains unclear.

Methods: PubMed, SCOPUS, and Web of Science were searched, followed by a two-phased screening by two independent researchers (IM & CQ). Risk of bias (Newcastle-Ottawa Scale), level of evidence and data collection were performed double-blind.

Results: Two cohort studies, 10 cross-sectional studies, and one case-control study were included. ANS function was measured by cardiovascular measurements (blood pressure, heart rate, and heart rate variability), sympathetic skin response, plasma catecholamines, and skin temperature. All studies used questionnaires to assess pain, nine used additional quantitative sensory testing. Significant associations between autonomic function (heart rate and blood pressure) and pain intensity (VAS) were found in patients with Irritable Bowel Syndrome ($p < 0.05$). Patients with chronic musculoskeletal pain showed significant associations between conditioned pain modulation and cardiac autonomic response ($p = 0.002$) and increased hyperalgesia ($p < 0.01$). Conflicting evidence was found for patients with Complex Regional Pain Syndrome and fibromyalgia. No significant associations were found in patients with chronic Whiplash Associated Disorders and chronic pancreatitis.

Conclusions: Both ANS and pain measurements were performed by a heterogeneous variety of assessments, creating a pitfall to provide a qualitative comparison of results. Therefore, this review provides insight into the potential involvement of autonomic pathways in pathological pain mechanisms in several chronic pain populations, but clearly urges the need for standardized measurements.

I-A.27

THE MISMATCH-HYPOTHESIS FOR CHRONIC PAIN – INTEGRATING INSIGHTS FROM ANCIENT, COMPARATIVE AND NEUROIMAGING GENOMICS

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Background and aims: An evolutionary perspective on chronic pain offers unique insights into the adaptive origins and vulnerabilities of the pain system. The mismatch hypothesis, a prominent concept in evolutionary medicine, posits that the gradual processes of evolution have failed to keep pace with the rapid changes and challenges of modern society, resulting in a mismatch between our biological predisposition and the demands of our environment. Despite its widespread popularity in evolutionary medicine, this theory currently lacks empirical support.

Methods: Here, we take advantage of a recent large-scale genome-wide association study (GWAS, $N = 164,178$) on chronic pain and publicly available GWAS data on brain morphology measures ($N = 33,000$) to investigate the influence of various evolutionary time scales on the genetic architecture of chronic pain and associated brain morphology. Furthermore, we test heritability enrichment for epigenetic influences, including epigenetic activity related to immune-diseases, and active marks in fetal human brain development.

Results: Our findings reveal a strong involvement of enhancer elements that emerged in the human lineage after our last common ancestor with Old World monkeys about 30 million years ago and of recent genetic changes within the last 100 generations. Conversely, we find no evolutionary enrichment signals for human accelerated